

Stress Analysis and Strength of Adhesive Bonded Joints under Bending Loads

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ABSTRACT

This study deals with a simple numerical method for the stress analysis of adhesive bonded structures subjected to bending loads based on the F.E.M. and experimental results of bending strength of single lap joints with an aluminum alloy adherend. For the numerical analysis of the bonded joint subjected to both the axial load and bending moment also considering the thermal expansion of adherends, the F.E.M. is introduced to solve the shear and normal stresses in the adhesive layer with an assumption that the adherends are considered as the one dimensional beam. Between the numerical and experimental results, good agreements are obtained.

INTRODUCTION

The structural adhesive joining technique is one of the effective method for composite materials. To design the reliable adhesive joint, more accurate but simple method for the stress analysis of adhesive bonded joints is desired. For the single lap joint, one may show the early work by Goland and Reissner[1] who analyzed stress distribution in the adhesive layer taking bending of the adherends into consideration. However, by their analytical method, it is very difficult to solve the problem having the thermal strain and more complicated boundary conditions. Many F.E.M. applications[2, 3] to the field of the stress analysis of adhesive joints are found and in most of them, the conventional finite element technique is used. For instance, both the adherends and adhesive layer are divided into plane strain finite elements.

This study describes the one dimensional F.E.M. which can analyze the shear and normal stresses in the adhesive layer of bonded structures taking both bending and thermal expansion of the adherends into consideration. The effects of lap length and taper angle at the lap ends on bending strength of the single lap joint subjected to pure bending moment are also reported.

GOVERNING EQUATIONS

Fig.1 represents the infinitesimal adhesive structure with the loads. In the same manner given by Goland and Reissner, equilibrium equations are obtained as follows.

For adherend (1)

$$\frac{dM^{(1)}}{dx} - V^{(1)} + \frac{1}{2} t^{(1)} \tau^{(a)} = 0$$

$$\frac{dV^{(1)}}{dx} - \sigma^{(a)} = 0$$

$$\frac{dT^{(1)}}{dx} - \tau^{(a)} = 0$$

For adherend (2)

$$\frac{dM^{(2)}}{dx} - V^{(2)} + \frac{1}{2} t^{(2)} \tau^{(a)} = 0$$

$$\frac{dV^{(2)}}{dx} + \sigma^{(a)} = 0$$

$$\frac{dT^{(2)}}{dx} + \tau^{(a)} = 0$$

(1)

(2)

Fig. 1 Force and stress components acting on an adhesive structural element

Upper suffix (1), (2) and (a) are indicate the adherends (1), (2) and adhesive layer, respectively. If $E^{(a)}$ and $G^{(a)}$ denote the Young's modulus and shear modulus of the adhesive, the shear stress $\tau^{(a)}$ and normal stress $\sigma^{(a)}$ of the adhesive layer are given in the following equations

$$\tau^{(a)} = G^{(a)} \gamma^{(a)} \quad \sigma^{(a)} = E^{(a)} \epsilon^{(a)} \quad (3)$$

where, $\gamma^{(a)}$ and $\epsilon^{(a)}$ denote the shear strain and normal strain of the adhesive, respectively. From Fig.2, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma^{(a)} &= \frac{1}{h} \left\{ (u^{(1)} - \frac{1}{2} t^{(1)} \theta^{(1)}) - (u^{(2)} + \frac{1}{2} t^{(2)} \theta^{(2)}) \right\} \\ &= \frac{1}{h} (u^{(1)} - u^{(2)}) + \frac{1}{2h} (-t^{(1)} \theta^{(1)} - t^{(2)} \theta^{(2)}) \\ &= \gamma_a^{(a)} + \gamma_b^{(a)} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where, u and θ are the axial displacements and the rotations of the adherends, respectively. $\gamma_a^{(a)}$ is the shear strain derived from the axial displacements, and $\gamma_b^{(a)}$ is the one from the effect of bending of the adherends.

From Fig.3, we obtain the following equation where w is the deflections of the adherends.

$$\epsilon^{(a)} = \frac{1}{h} (w^{(1)} - w^{(2)}) \quad (5)$$

Fig. 2 Relative displacement

Fig. 3 Relative deflection

FORMULATION OF THE F.E.M.

The bonded structural region is divided into finite elements as shown in Fig.4(a). Now i -th element is considered. The displacements (axial displacement, deflection, and rotation) and corresponding forces (axial force, shear force and bending moment) of each nodal point of this element are shown in Fig.4(b). Each axial displacement ($u^{(1)}$, $u^{(2)}$) of the adherends is interpolated linearly by the nodal displacements.

$$\{u\} = \begin{Bmatrix} u_{ij}^{(1)} \\ u_{ij}^{(2)} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} [Nu] & \{0\}^T \\ \{0\}^T & [Nu] \end{Bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \{u_{ij}^{(1)}\} \\ \{u_{ij}^{(2)}\} \end{Bmatrix} = [\bar{Nu}] \{\bar{u}_{ij}\} \quad (6)$$

Fig.4 Finite element division / Nodal forces and displacements

$[Nu]$ is the displacement function for the axial displacement of the adherend. It is given by

$$[Nu] = [L_1 \quad L_2] \quad (7)$$

where, L_1 and L_2 are natural coordinates in the natural coordinate system of one dimensional beam element, and they can be related to the global coordinate system.

Similarly, the deflection $\{w\}$ is represented by the third-ordered interpolating function, then we have

$$\{w\} = \begin{Bmatrix} w^{(1)} \\ w^{(2)} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} [Nw] & \{0\}^T \\ \{0\}^T & [Nw] \end{Bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \{w_{ij}^{(1)}\} \\ \{w_{ij}^{(2)}\} \end{Bmatrix} = [\bar{N}w] \{\bar{w}_{ij}\} \quad (8)$$

where

$$[Nw] = [L_1^2(3-2L_1) \quad -L_1^2L_2 \quad L_2^2(3-2L_2) \quad L_1L_2^2]$$

$$\{\bar{w}_{ij}^1\} = \begin{Bmatrix} w_i^{(1)} \\ \theta_i^{(1)} \\ w_j^{(1)} \\ \theta_j^{(1)} \end{Bmatrix} \quad \{\bar{w}_{ij}^2\} = \begin{Bmatrix} w_i^{(2)} \\ \theta_i^{(2)} \\ w_j^{(2)} \\ \theta_j^{(2)} \end{Bmatrix}$$

The rotation $\{\theta\}$ is obtained by differentiating the $\{w\}$ with x

$$\{\theta\} = \frac{d}{dx} \{w\} = \begin{Bmatrix} -\frac{d}{dx}[Nb] & \{0\}^T \\ \{0\}^T & -\frac{d}{dx}[Nb] \end{Bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \{\bar{w}_{ij}^1\} \\ \{\bar{w}_{ij}^2\} \end{Bmatrix} = [\bar{N}_\theta] \{\bar{w}_{ij}\} \quad (9)$$

Total strain energy of the bonded element is given by the following equation.

$$\pi = \pi^{(1)} + \pi^{(2)} + \pi^{(a)} \quad (10)$$

where $\pi^{(1)}$, $\pi^{(2)}$ and $\pi^{(a)}$ denote the strain energy of the adherends (1), (2) and adhesive layer, respectively. $\pi^{(1)}$ and $\pi^{(2)}$ are the sum of the strain energy corresponding to the axial and bending displacement of the adherend. $\pi^{(a)}$ is the sum of the shear strain energy $\pi_\tau^{(a)}$ and normal strain energy $\pi_\sigma^{(a)}$. The shear strain $\gamma^{(a)}$ and normal strain $\epsilon^{(a)}$ of the adhesive layer are written in matrix forms

$$\gamma^{(a)} = \frac{1}{h} [1 \quad -1] [\bar{N}u] \{\bar{u}_{ij}\} - \frac{1}{2h} [t^{(1)} \quad t^{(2)}] [\bar{N}_\theta] \{\bar{w}_{ij}\} = \frac{1}{2h} [\bar{N}_\gamma^{(a)}] \{d\} \quad (11)$$

$$\epsilon^{(a)} = \frac{1}{h} [1 \quad -1] \begin{Bmatrix} w^{(1)} \\ w^{(2)} \end{Bmatrix} = \frac{1}{h} [1 \quad -1] [\bar{N}w] \{\bar{w}_{ij}\} = \frac{1}{h} [\bar{N}_\epsilon^{(a)}] \{\bar{w}_{ij}\} \quad (12)$$

where,

$$\{d\}^T = [u_i^{(1)} \quad w_i^{(1)} \quad \theta_i^{(1)} \quad u_j^{(1)} \quad w_j^{(1)} \quad \theta_j^{(1)} \quad u_i^{(2)} \quad w_i^{(2)} \quad \theta_i^{(2)} \quad u_j^{(2)} \quad w_j^{(2)} \quad \theta_j^{(2)}]$$

If B is the width of the element, we have

$$\pi_\tau^{(a)} = \frac{1}{2} \int_{Vol^{(a)}} \tau^{(a)} \gamma^{(a)} dV = \frac{1}{2} Bh \int_1 \tau^{(a)} \gamma^{(a)} dx = \frac{1}{2} \frac{BG^{(a)}}{4h} \int_1 \{d\}^T [\bar{N}_\gamma^{(a)}]^T [\bar{N}_\gamma^{(a)}] \{d\} dx \quad (13)$$

$$\pi_\sigma^{(a)} = \frac{1}{2} \int_{Vol^{(a)}} \sigma^{(a)} \epsilon^{(a)} dV = \frac{1}{2} Bh \int_1 \sigma^{(a)} \epsilon^{(a)} dx = \frac{1}{2} \frac{BE^{(a)}}{h} \int_1 \{\bar{w}_{ij}\}^T [\bar{N}_\epsilon^{(a)}]^T [\bar{N}_\epsilon^{(a)}] \{\bar{w}_{ij}\} dx \quad (14)$$

The effect of thermal expansion of the adherends by temperature rise can be included as the initial strain of them. Consequently, we have the following stiffness equation of the element

$$([k_m] + [k^{(a)}]) \{d\} = \{f\} + \{f_t\} \quad (15)$$

where, $\{f\}$ is the external force, $\{f_t\}$ is the nodal force due to thermal expansion.

$$\begin{aligned} \{f\}^T &= [P_i^{(1)} \quad V_i^{(1)} \quad M_i^{(1)} \quad P_j^{(1)} \quad V_j^{(1)} \quad M_j^{(1)} \quad P_i^{(2)} \quad V_i^{(2)} \quad M_i^{(2)} \quad P_j^{(2)} \quad V_j^{(2)} \quad M_j^{(2)}] \\ \{f_t\}^T &= [P_{ti}^{(1)} \quad 0 \quad 0 \quad P_{tj}^{(1)} \quad 0 \quad 0 \quad P_{ti}^{(2)} \quad 0 \quad 0 \quad P_{tj}^{(2)} \quad 0 \quad 0] \end{aligned}$$

$[k_m]$ is the same as the stiffness matrix of a beam element of the adherends (1) and (2). We find that $[k_m]$ consist of two stiffness matrixes $[k_m^{(1)}]$ and $[k_m^{(2)}]$ delived from each adherend individually.

$$[k_m] = \begin{bmatrix} [k_m^{(1)}] & [0] \\ [0] & [k_m^{(2)}] \end{bmatrix} \quad (16)$$

The stiffness matrix derived from the adhesive stiffness $[k^{(a)}]$ is the sum of the stiffness matrixes for shear and normal displacements, $[k_\tau^{(a)}]$ and $[k_\sigma^{(a)}]$. It is given by

$$[k^{(a)}] = [k_\tau^{(a)}] + [k_\sigma^{(a)}] \quad (17)$$

where

$$[k_\tau^{(a)}] = \frac{B}{4h} G^{(a)} \int_1 [\bar{N}_Y^{(a)}]^T [\bar{N}_Y^{(a)}] dx \quad [k_\sigma^{(a)}] = \frac{B}{h} E^{(a)} \int_1 [\bar{N}_E^{(a)}]^T [\bar{N}_E^{(a)}] dx$$

EXPERIMENTS

Experiments for evaluating the numerical method

Two kinds of experiment are conducted to verify the availability of the numerical method formulated in this study. One of these experiments is a three-point bending test using a stiffened thin plate shown in Fig.5. In order to obtain the deflection in detail, a double exposure holographic interferometry is applied. An aluminum plate is used for the test specimen. The other experiment is the test to examine the effect of thermal strain of the adhesive bonded sandwich beam which consists of two different materials having different coefficients of thermal expansion. Strain gages are mounted on both surfaces of the specimen as shown in Fig.6 in order to compare this result to the calculated one. The test specimen in an electric oven is simply supported on both ends. Materials used for the specimen are steel (SS41) and aluminum (7075T06).

Fig.5 Stiffened plate for three-point bending test

Fig.6 Illustration of thermal effect test and location of strain gages

Fig. 7 Illustration of four-point bending test

Bending test

A series of four-point bending test shown in Fig. 7 is conducted on the single lap joint specimens of which dimensions are shown in Fig. 8 in order to know the effects of lap length and taper angle on bending strength. An aluminum alloy (7075T06) are used as the adherend. The adherend of which lap surface is polished and cleaned by acetone, are bonded by Alardite (AW106: HV953U=10:8 wt.)

Fig. 8 Single lap joint specimen for four-point bending test

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Evaluation of the numerical method

Photo.1 shows the holography interference of the aluminum stiffened plate obtained from the three-point bending test. Those fringes represent the equivalent deflection curves. Because a pin-pointed load is applied at the center of the specimen, these curves are concave a little at both edges of the plate. The deflection at the center line is compared to the calculated result. The comparison is shown in Fig. 9. The material constants used in this analysis are shown in Tabel.1. As for the thermal strain, relations between upper and lower surface strains of the sandwich beam obtained experimentally are compared to ones calculated as shown in Fig. 12. Excellent agreements between experimental results and calculated ones are found in both cases. It is confirmed that the simple numerical method based on the F.E.M. which is given in this study is effective to analyze the adhesive stresses with the interaction of axial stress, bending moment and thermal strain. Some typical cases calculated for the adhesive structure which are used to compare to the experiment are shown in Fig. 10. Fig. 10 shows the shear and normal (peeling) stress distributions in the adhesive layer when the stiffened plate is subjected to the three-point bending load. It indicates the effect of the lap length of the adhesive layer on the adhesive stresses. Each stress is normalized by the applied load per unit

Photo.1 Fringe pattern of stiffened plate

Fig. 9 Deflection curve of stiffened plate

Table 1. Material constant for calculation

Stell	Aluminum	Adhesive
E=210 (GPa) $\alpha=14.0 \times 10^6$ (1/K°)	E=70 (GPa) $\alpha=22.5 \times 10^5$ (1/K°)	E ^a =3 (GPa) $\alpha^a=1$ (GPa) H = 0.1 (mm)

α ; coefficient of thermal expansion

Fig.10 Adhesive stress distribution under three-point bending load

Fig.11 Effect of lap length of stiffener on maximum adhesive stresses

width $p = P/B$. In the case of three-point bending test, the maximum shear and normal stresses decrease with increase of the lap length as shown in Fig.11, but their decreasing ratios are small compared to the increasing ratio of lap length.

It is found in Fig.10 that the shear and normal stress distributions change according to the lap length but only in the vicinity of the lap end, the considerably large stresses exist, therefore in this case, the large stresses are limited in the short length near the lap end and this length is nearly constant.

Fig.12 Relation between surface thermal strain and temperature rise

The area where the normal stress is positive (tension) and effective on the adhesive failure is also limited within 1.5mm long. It is considered that the reason why the maximum shear and normal stresses decrease with increase of the lap length is derived from the reduction of actual bending moment applied at the lap end because of the three point-bending test. If the lap length increases from 20mm to 40mm, the bending moment applied at the lap end decreases to 3/4, therefore each maximum stress also decreases to 3/4 of its initial value. The effect of the lap length on the adhesive stresses is caused mainly by change of the bending moment at the lap end, therefore as the span increases, the effect of the lap length on adhesive stresses would be reduced. On the other hand, the change of the thickness of the adhesive layer does not have much effect on the tendency of stress distributions along the lap but has much effect on the maximum adhesive stresses and they increase as the thickness decreases.

Experimental results of bending strength

Fig.13 shows the relation between the bending strength of the single lap joint and the lap length L. In this experiment, the increase of strength suddenly diminishes after the lap length being more than 20mm. The curve of bending strength versus overlap length tends to become asymptotic to a certain maximum value. Fig.14 shows the calculated shear and normal stress distributions along the adhesive layer of the single lap joint subjected to pure bending moment. When the lap length is more than 10mm the maximum shear and normal stresses become constant even if the lap length increases. The area where the meaningful stresses exist is limited and almost 5-6mm long from the lap end. Also, the increase of lap length of the specimen having more than a certain length does not increase the bending strength. In this case, if the lap length increases from 20mm to 40mm, the bending moment applied at the lap end is constant. These result suggest that the three-point bending test usually used to measure the bending strength of single lap bonded joints is not appropriate method because of the change of bending moment through the lap. To evaluate the bending strength the pure bending test for the specimen having a certain lap length is recommended.

Fig.15 shows the relation between the bending strength of the single lap joint with taper at the lap ends and the taper angle. It is well estimated from the numerical result shown in Fig.14 that the maximum bonded stresses at the lap end do not decrease even if the lap length increases, and also the part where the large stress occurs is limited near the lap end. Therefore, it is supposed that the stress concentration can be reduced by decreasing the stiffness to bending and normal displacement. Ref.3 reported that the effect of taper on single lap joint is useful to improve the tensile shear strength of it. Our test result also shows that the taper on the adherend is effective to increase the bending strength of the bonded joints.

Fig.13 Effect of lap length on bending strength of single lap joint subjected to pure bending moment

Fig.15 Effect of taper angle on bending strength of single lap joint subjected to pure bending moment

Fig.14 Adhesive stress distributions of single lap joint subjected to pure bending moment

CONCLUSIONS

- (1) The simple numerical method based on the F.E.M. taking the reciprocal action of axial force, bending moment and thermal strain into account is developed and examined its availability.
- (2) The pure bending test is desired to evaluate the bending strength of simple lap joints.
- (3) The bending strength of single lap joints is improved using the adherend tapered on its lap end

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